

THE SILENT STRUGGLE OF GREEN COSMETICS IN EMERGING MARKETS : AN INDONESIAN CASE ON CONSUMER PSYCHOLOGY AND PURCHASE INTENTION

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Abstract. As global interest in sustainable goods continues to rise, eco-friendly cosmetics are attracting increasing attention. However, in contrast to the worldwide growth trend, Indonesia still lags in both awareness and usage of green cosmetics. This research explores the key factors influencing the intention of Indonesian consumers to purchase green cosmetics. It employs the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) as the foundational framework. Within this model, central variables include personal attitudes and perceived social influences (subjective norms). Furthermore, the framework is expanded by adding consumers' knowledge about green cosmetics and their altruistic drive as supporting dimensions. Attitude is also analyzed in this study as a mediating variable. Data collection was carried out using a quantitative approach through an online questionnaire distributed between April and May 2025. The sample comprised 206 Indonesian users of green cosmetics selected through convenience sampling. Data were analyzed using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) with the SmartPLS4 software.

Keywords: Green cosmetics, Purchase intention, Attitude, Altruistic Motivation, Subjective Norms, Indonesia, TPB, Consumer Behavior.

1. Introduction

The scarcity of natural resources and the worsening climate pose a significant threat to the sustainability of the planet and human well-being (Teixeira et al., 2023). Nowadays, consumers have shown growing awareness of the product origins, production process, environmental impact, and safety of products, particularly in the cosmetics industry (Ferreira & Santos, 2022; Teixeira et al., 2023). Global beauty has seen significant growth due to increased competition and consumer preference when consuming products (Radhi, 2025). Likewise, Indonesia also has shown a notable 21,9% growth in the cosmetics industry with the number of companies rising from 913 in 2022 to 1,010 by mid-2023 (Coordinating Ministry for Economics, 2024). This growth has brought various challenges to the cosmetics industry in Indonesia, including for green cosmetics which face similar issues. Consumers are becoming more inclined toward green cosmetics, valuing their ability to protect the skin, and minimizing environmental harm (Mamun et al., 2020). Indonesian consumer's awareness of green cosmetics is still relatively low, as shown in Databoks survey that only 30,6% of consumers have purchased sustainable health and cosmetics products within the past year (Jayani, 2021). Statista forecasts that the global market for green cosmetics will hit USD 13.86 billion by 2024, with an expected yearly growth of 6.11% until 2029. However, in Indonesia, the projected revenue is only USD 251 million with an estimated annual increase of 5.33% during the same timeframe (Trimahanani, 2024). The significant difference reflects the low adoption and transaction levels in Indonesia, proving that green cosmetics remain low priority among Indonesian consumers. This phenomenon reveals an issue with consumer purchase intention in the green cosmetics industry. Aligning with (Limbu et al., 2022), which emphasizes that understanding consumer's purchase intention is important for marketers.

Although green cosmetics are growing rapidly, the level of awareness among Indonesian people remains low with 45% of respondents admitting that they do not understand regarding eco-friendly products (Karyoko, 2024; Limbu et al., 2022). Indonesia's strong sense of collectivism reinforces the impact of subjective norms (Limbu et al., 2022; Mubtasir, 2025). Nevertheless, environmental awareness remains low, as reflected in the fact that only 15.5% of Indonesians actively look for environmental information highlighting weak altruistic motivation (Alam et al., 2023; Sembiring,

2023). Research by (Dlamini & Mahowa, 2024) also shows that attitude is considered a major factor in encouraging the intention to purchase eco-conscious cosmetics. Comprehensive research that examines these variables with attitude as a mediating remains limited, especially in a culturally and environmentally diverse country like Indonesia. Hence, this study seeks to explore what drives consumer decisions to purchase green cosmetics and how these factors relate to purchase intention. The study utilizes the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) as its theoretical framework.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Purchase Intentions

In recent years, Eco-conscious beauty products have attracted growing attention from both academic researchers and the professional industry. Purchase intention represents the probability and interest of consumers to make a purchase, which is formed on the basis of needs, personal preferences, and the perceptions of the product (Olfat, 2025; Zhang et al., 2023; Mamun et al., 2020). Positive tendency towards environmental issues and green cosmetic products for some consumers are not guaranteed to lead to purchases, which still indicates hesitance to make sustainable purchases (Venciute et al., 2023). It is also critical to identifying these underlying influence in order to stimulate increased sustainable purchase intention.

2.2 Green Cosmetics Knowledge

Increased numbers of environmental-sensitive consumers have also led to significant changes in the purchase intention of consumers (Moslehpour et al., 2023). Green cosmetics knowledge can be viewed as an information that is retained in the memory of the consumer and affects the preferences, which is also a factor in developing the behavior and the purchase intention towards green cosmetics (Wang et al., 2019). Green knowledge can be gauged taking above green products knowledge, environmental knowledge, product usage knowledge and expectations toward the effect of green products to the environment (Faizah et al., 2023).Lack of knowledge has been shown to be a barrier to the adoption of innovations in various sectors, so increasing consumer knowledge in the context of green cosmetics is key to driving purchase intention (Alalaiwat, 2025; AlHaj, 2022).

2.3 Subjective Norms

Subjective norms describe how individuals consider societal expectations or peer influence when choosing to adopt or avoid specific behaviors (Teixeira et al., 2023). The social effect is likely to have a stronger impact on behavior, as consumers are aware of the potential consequences in their minds (Kumar & Pandey, 2023). Subjective norms consist of two interrelated components, which are the belief in significant others who are considered important to encourage certain behaviors and the motivation to comply with these referent expectations (Yulfinarsyah, 2021). In the context of green products, subjective norms are one of the strongest determinants of purchase intention (Ngo-Thi-Ngoc et al., 2024;Griskevicius et al., 2010).

2.4 Altruistic Motivation

Altruism reflects an individual's concern for others welfare, where altruistic values encourage individuals to show deep concern without personal gain (Caniëls et al., 2021). Five main aspects make altruistic one of them is compassion, helpfulness, taking into account other people, empathy, and readiness to sacrifice (Mazaya et al., 2024). As far as eco-friendly cosmetics is concerned, subjective norms have been found to exert an influence that positively affects the probability of consumers to buy green products (Alam et al., 2023; Pop et al., 2020).

2.5 Attitude

In addition to protecting nature, consumers with high levels of environmental awareness prefer to use eco-friendly products because of individual gain; their environmental attitudes are important factors that affect their purchase intention (Teixeira et al., 2023). Such attitudes are not settled and can even change whenever individuals acquire new information or experience new situations concerning environmental issues (Gul et al., 2021). The organizational attitudes usually consist of the three basic dimensions, namely affective (emotional response), cognitive (thoughts and beliefs), and conative (intentions of action) (Ajzen, 1991; Widjaja et al., 2020).

According to previous research, positive attitudes toward environment-friendly products are able to significantly boost one purchase intention (Lili et al., 2022; Tan et al., 2022). In order to give a summary of the relationship between the variables mentioned above, the researcher demonstrated a general research model as pictured in Figure 1. This diagram sets out a clear visual representation of the associations of the variables under investigation and this forms the foundation of the hypothesis, which has been proposed in the present research.

Figure 2.1 Research Model

H1: The effect of knowledge about green cosmetics on the purchase intention is positive.

H2: Subjective norms have a positive effect on purchase intention.

H3: Altruistic motive has a positive effect on purchase intention.

H4: Purchase intention is affected positively by attitude. H5: Knowledge about green cosmetics positively influences purchase intention through the mediating role of attitude.

H6: Subjective norms positively influence purchase intention through the mediating role of attitude.

H7: Altruistic motivation positively influences purchase intention through the mediating role of attitude.

3. Methodology

This study adopts a quantitative research method by distributing an online survey through social media platforms between April and May 2025. The variable of attitude functions as a mediating factor, representing broader psychological patterns highlighted in earlier studies (Ramos et al., 2022). Responses were measured using a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from (1) “Strongly disagree” to (5) “Strongly agree.” Participants were chosen using convenience sampling and consisted of green cosmetics users in Indonesia. The collected data includes demographic information and 29 question items that assess the core variables of the research. These constructs were adapted from the prior research (Alam et al., 2023; Long & Krause, 2017; Pop et al., 2020; Silintowe & Sukresna, 2022; Teixeira et al., 2023) with green cosmetics knowledge, subjective norms, and altruistic motivation as independent variables. While purchase intention serves as the dependent variable and attitude functions as a mediator. Data analysis was carried out using SmartPLS 4 software, applying the Structural Equation Modeling - Partial Least Squares (SEM-PLS) method. The results were obtained through the PLS-SEM algorithm and evaluated using the basic bootstrapping technique.

4. Results and Discussion

A total of 206 participants were involved in this study. The demographic details, outlined in Table 1, show that 90.3% female participants made up the majority of the sample, with only 9.7% being male. Furthermore, 53.4% of the respondents were between the ages of 17 and 25. Most participants reside in Tangerang, with students making up 38.8% and private-sector employees comprising 31.6% of the sample.

Table 1. Demographic profile of respondents

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	20	9.7
Female	186	90.3
Age (years)		
17-25	110	53.4
26-35	35	17
> 35	61	29.6
Occupation		
Homemaker	39	18.9
Private Employee	65	31.6
Civil Servant	7	3.4
Student	80	38.8
Entrepreneur	13	6.3
Other	2	1
Domicile		
Jakarta	54	26.2
Bogor	12	5.8
Depok	5	2.4
Tangerang	127	61.7
Bekasi	8	3.9

4.1 Measurement Model

As shown in Table 2 presents the value of discriminant validity. According to the convergent validity, satisfactory construct validity is achieved when all indicators exhibit factor loadings above 0.60 (Hair et al., 2016; Aulia et al., 2023) Therefore, the data were in line with the criteria.

Table 2. Outer Loading Value

Construct	A	AM	GCK	PI	SN
A1	0.866				
A2	0.906				
A3	0.919				
A4	0.884				
AM1		0.806			
AM2		0.753			
AM3		0.793			
AM4		0.789			
AM5		0.816			
AM6		0.869			
AM7		0.764			
GCK1			0.731		
GCK2			0.739		
GCK3			0.758		
GCK4			0.643		
GCK5			0.725		
GCK6			0.716		
PI1				0.780	
PI2				0.874	
PI3				0.820	
PI4				0.876	
PI5				0.833	
SN1					0.771
SN2					0.752
SN3					0.794
SN4					0.703
SN5					0.760
SN6					0.801
SN7					0.775

As shown in table 3, it displays Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability values for each construct. As stated by (Raharjanti et al., 2022), the construct is deemed reliable if both values exceed 0.7, indicating strong internal consistency. Additionally, an Average Variance Extracted (AVE) score above 0.5 confirms good convergent validity (Lili et al., 2022). Therefore, all constructs used in this study can be considered both valid and reliable.

Table 3. Reability Analysis

Constructs	α	CRA	CR C	AVE
Attitude	0.916	0.916	0.941	0.799
Altruistic motivation	0.905	0.907	0.925	0.639
Green cosmetics knowledge	0.813	0.813	0.865	0.518
Purchase intention	0.893	0.895	0.921	0.701
Subjective norms	0.884	0.893	0.908	0.586

Note : α = Cronbach's alpha; CR = composite reliability; AVE = average variance extracted

To further understand the connection between variables, Table 4 presents the path coefficient that reflects both direct and indirect effects in the model. These results are based on the path coefficient analysis and specific indirect effect, providing a comprehensive view of the influence exerted by each construct.

Table 4. Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis	Path	Std. Beta	M	Std. Dev	T values	P values	Result
H1	GCK→PI	0.163	0.164	0.087	1.876	0.061	Rejected
H2	SN→PI	0.230	0.232	0.070	3.281	0.001	Accepted
H3	AM→PI	0.321	0.323	0.084	3.813	0.000	Accepted
H4	A→PI	0.210	0.205	0.074	2.828	0.005	Accepted
H5	GCK→A→PI	0.029	0.029	0.015	1.893	0.058	Rejected
H6	SN→A→PI	0.003	0.003	0.011	0.289	0.772	Rejected
H7	AM→A→PI	0.157	0.154	0.056	2.787	0.005	Accepted

Based on the hypothesis testing shown in Table 4, the findings reveal that knowledge about green cosmetics in the Indonesian context does not significantly influence consumers' intention to purchase these products ($\beta = 0.163$, t -value < 1.96 , $p > 0.05$). Therefore, hypothesis H1 is not supported. In contrast, hypotheses H2, H3, and H4 received empirical support. Specifically, subjective norms ($\beta = 0.230$), altruistic motivation ($\beta = 0.321$), and attitude ($\beta = 0.210$) all exhibited statistically significant and positive effects on consumers' intention to purchase green cosmetics, as each t -value exceeded 1.96 and each p -value was below 0.05. These outcomes suggest that social influence, moral concern for others, and individuals' attitudes meaningfully drive Indonesian consumers' intentions to buy eco-friendly cosmetic products.

Regarding the indirect relationship, the study found that consumers' knowledge about green cosmetics does not significantly impact purchase intention when the effect is mediated by attitude. The output showed ($= 0.029$, t -values < 1.96 , p -values > 0.05) indicates that H5 is rejected. It emerged later, that when attitude served as a mediator in mediating purchase intention, the subjective norms did not have significant effect. H6 is stated as rejected against the output ($= 0.003$, t -values < 1.96 , p -values > 0.05). On the contrary, altruistic motivation had a significant indirect effect on the purchase intention by way of attitude. H7 is said to be accepted with respect to result obtained ($= 0.157$, t -values > 1.96 , p -values < 0.05).

Unlike a study conducted in Taiwan and Vietnam (Limbu et al., 2022; Moslehpour et al., 2023), in-depth information known about green cosmetic among Indonesian consumers does not extensively impact buying intention. This reveals that the awareness of green cosmetics does not always mean that Indonesian consumers are motivated to purchase them as knowledge is insufficient proving their intentions to buy (Sholihah & Harsoyo, 2023; Wiranto & Adialita, 2020). In its place, the great influence of subjective norms on purchasing intention indicates that the use of green products in Indonesia is the outcome of pressure or social environment similar to that in Vietnam and Malaysia (Ngo-Thi-Ngoc et al., 2024; Sapri et al., 2023). Consumers social and environmentally concerned were mostly found to purchase green cosmetics, as it was also identified in consumers in Saudi, Romania, and Hungary (Alam et al., 2023; Pop et al., 2020). A positive influence of attitude on purchase intention is direct (Dlamini & Mahowa, 2024; Ruangkanjanases et al., 2020).

Nevertheless, the present research concluded that the attitude does not mediate the relationship between green knowledge and purchase intention, which was not observed in the literature (Dlamini & Mahowa, 2024; Geralvine et al., 2025), and it is possible to state that there were certain incongruities in this theory. There is also no strong indirect impact of subjective norms on attitude, which is supported by Backer & AP (2024), whose assumption is that social pressure does not necessarily result in a favourable attitude generated in the presence of a conflict with personal values. On the other hand, altruistic motivation has a major impact on attitude positively influencing on green buying decision.

The result is consistent with what Steinbiß et al. (2022) found, to the extent that altruism may promote environmental regard attitudes, which may heighten the likelihood of customers buying green products. These findings imply that although knowledge and subjective norms might not significantly make a difference, practically, altruistic motivation is an influential factor contributing to the development of consumer attitude and enhancing the intention in procuring green products.

5. Conclusion

This research was conducted to understand how the green cosmetic knowledge, social norms, altruistic motivation and personal attitudes impact potential purchases of eco-friendly cosmetics among the populations of the Greater Jakarta (Jakarta, Bogor, Depok, Tangerang, and Bekasi). The findings indicate that product knowledge do not strongly affect the purchase intention of an Indonesian consumer as it does in some other countries where it acts individually. Other predictors that become more crucial are subjective norms, altruism, and attitude. The results indicate a possibility that emotional and social motives can dominate over cognitive influences on the development of green purchasing behavior. Additionally, although knowledge, social influence did not have a significant impact on purchase intention via attitude, altruistic motives indicated that internal moral values impact the development of positive attitudes and stimulate the purchase intention of being ecologically-conscious. Such findings emphasize the fact that ethical and emotional communicues can be very potent in green product promotion campaigns. Brands, to engage with Indonesian consumers, should create an ethical connection and use influencing power via social influence and create campaigns that are representative of what they hold dear. In the future, one should examine the offers of computer technologies, in particular, social networks by the way of supporting and strengthening pro environmental norms and altruistic behavior. The analysis of the contribution of the eco-influencers and the content created by peers can provide additional information on sustainable consumer behavior in Indonesia.

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